

Archaeoastronomy of Kukulkan´ Pyramid Using an Approximate Squaring the Circle Construction Part II

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Abstract

On this work a model to establish the relation between a geometrical construction of "Squaring the Circle" and "Descending Snake" phenomenon on Kukulkan´ Pyramid was analyzed. The model presents the relation between other geometrical and astronomical objects (straight line, ellipsoid and apparent diameter of the Sun).

Keyword: Archaeoastronomy; Architecture; Maya; Astronomy

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* Model 1

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2 Model 1

* Establish a reference point on sky (definition of measure using stars)

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* Establish idea of projection of the star position

* Establish trajectories

Scheme 1. Blue := Central point of reference; Pink := Points of start and end of general trajectories through

* Establish how many days have passed since the observation of some point of reference until the repetition of same scenario (around 365 days);

* Establish that sometimes the number of days is different (the same scenario can be seen in a number of days different from 365)

* Establish that the trajectory defines next three geometrical facts

- The shape of earth is spherical (since the trajectory that is an straight line)

- The trajectory of the earth around a central point is non spherical (from the counting of days)

- The earth have an inclination (since the two general trajectories that are not an straight line)

3 Model 2

* Establish that relation between stars trajectories through days can be described around a central square using the circles to represent the earth position around the sun

* Establish the relation between circle and square through a geometrical property (i.e. "Squaring the Circle")

* Establish the relation between square like base of levels of Kukulkan' Pyramid and circle like sun position to achieve the "Descent of the Serpent".

4 Analysis Model 1

The model described on this text will use like main point of reference "Pleyade" star (see QA1).

Other stars like Sirius (α Canis Majoris), Vega (α Lyrae); Capella (α Aurigae) and Antares (α Scorpii) also have a regular sighting.

Pleyade appears on cenit position at night between September and January; from 0400 to 2000 hrs. The rest of the year have culmination at evening or during day. While peak of observation happen on November (around 00:00 hrs at 15th day).

[Pleiades Occultation by the Moon at Wikipedia](#)

Pleyade Position in November 2025

Pleyade position in December 2025

Pleyade position in January 2026

[Map of Kukulcan Pyramid at SunEarthTools](#)

Regularity and ease of observation could be used by ancient Mayans to establish the idea of projection of the position of an object on the ground to define a measure of the passage of time.

Noticing last fact can be established that the trajectory of the Pleyade defines three main courses; considering that north and south has already been defined.

* An straight line

Map of Kukulcan´ Pyramid with Sun Position: Straight Line of Sun Position

* Exit and hiding from the North

Map of Kukulcan´ Pyramid with Sun Position: Exit and hiding from the North

* Exit and hiding from the South

Map of Kukulkan´ Pyramid with Sun Position: Exit and hiding from the South

Before the establishment of the definition of latitude, declination of a star, and azimuth angle; the difference in trajectories must be the main measure to establish the inclination of earth and shape of earth [see scheme 1] .

Like the star always appear from left to right going through different trajectories, this fact could have led to the discovery that earth was a "regular three dimensional object" and the discovery of spherical shapes

Using an scheme similar to 1; the exit angle of a star could be measure. Like the measure of the position of the sun it is usually uncomfortable for the human eyes; this measure could be made on a star at night.

If the straight line that made the sun at equinox is taken like an horizontal, and the angle regarding the exit of the sun at another time of the year (i.e. the "angular separation above the horizon between the east -equinox- and the azimuth of sunrise on that other date") is considered the value calculated is around 23° - 25° degrees [see QA2] .

Note:

*The exit azimuth since North is

$$\cos A = \frac{\sin \delta}{\cos \phi}$$

with

ϕ := Latitude

δ := Sun declination on day

While the angle of separation since East (Equinox) is:

$$\Delta = 90 - A = \arcsin\left(\frac{\sin \delta}{\cos \phi}\right)$$

$\Delta > 0$:= Exit to the North East (Spring - Summer on the North hemisphere)

$\Delta < 0$:= Exit to the East to the South East (Autumn - Winter)

-Maximum Value

Sun declination is maximum on Solstices with $\delta = \pm\epsilon$, with $\epsilon \approx 23.44$

- Maximum Value at Yucatan, Mexico ($\phi \approx 21$)

* $\cos \phi \approx 0.933$

* $\sin \epsilon \approx 0.398$

$\Delta \approx \arcsin\left(\frac{0.398}{0.933}\right) \approx 25.2$

On Yucatan the Sun on solstices exit at ~ 25 to North East (June) or ~ 25 to South East (December), regarding the straight line of equinox

It means the same as the tilt of the earth.

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5 Analysis of Model 2

Pleyade position on the sky its related with "ecliptic plane"; i.e. the orbital plane of Earth around the Sun; and also the plane where Equinox happen.

While sun trajectory from East to West depends of Earth rotation, varying with latitude; Pleyade align partially with ecliptic.

It is important to note that Pleyade and Sun exit angle are equal ($\delta \approx +24$) on Summer Solstice (~ 22). On June Pleyades are in Solar conjunction; this means that Pleyade are invisible because they are behind Sun. Also they have same Zenith.

Now lets consider next graph about Squaring the Circle [1]

[Graph Earth Orbit with Square and Circles No Rotate](#)

[Open Office Calc Book fo Kukulkan´ Squaring Part II](#)

Graph of 1.- (Light Green; Eq. 1) Ellipsoid; 2.- (Gray, Red, Blue Eq. 6, 7, 8, 9) Circles; 3.- Square

Remember that Ellipsoid equation is

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$$

where

a := major semi axis

b := minor semi axis

For the Ellipsoid that describes the Earth orbit around Sun

$a = 149.6$ millions of Km

$b = 149.5791376$ millions of Km

On graph 1 this ellipsoid is shown on light green

Now lets take the foci equation

$$c = \sqrt{a^2 - b^2}$$

with foci coordinates on

$$F_1 = (c, 0) \quad ; \quad F_2 = (-c, 0)$$

For the ellipsoid of Earth orbit

$c = 2.49832$ millions of Km (eq 2, eq 3)

While "Latus rectum" equation is

$$L = \frac{2b^2}{a}$$

$L_1 = -147.0599581$ millions of Km (eq 4)

$L_2 = 147.0599581$ millions of Km (eq 5)

Now using the coordinates of "Latus Rectum" like the center of a circle (eq 6, eq 7) .

With

$$(x - a')^2 + (y - b')^2 = r^2$$

Now lets consider the ref [1] to obtain the square related (eq. h and eq. g)

$$g : \quad y = x + 2.49832 \quad ;$$

$$h : \quad y = -x + 2.49832$$

Now consider the diagonal of an square of sides

$$l = r\sqrt{\pi}$$

To obtain the remaining sides (eq. p, eq. q)

$$p : y = x + 187.443504201 + 187.4435042401$$

$$q : y = -x + 187.443504201 + 187.4435042401$$

Graph screenshot with equations 1

And lets obtain the circles of eq. 8 and eq. 9

Graph screenshot with equations 2

Now consider the graph rotated 23°

The graph was rotated on PAINT.NET

Now lets consider next geometrical fact [see QA3]

The Sun seen since Earth is not a point but a disk. This circle has an angle radius that depends of the distance Earth-Sun in each moment of the year.

The apparent diameter of the Sun is approximately 0.53° (around 32 minutes of arc); i.e. its angular radius is approximately 0.265° (around 16 minutes of arc).

On Perihelium is around 32.7°

On Aphelium is around 31.6°

Now lets calculate the angular distance of the sun for a disk of radius

Level	aprox. side LL (m)	Radius $R = \frac{L}{\sqrt{\pi R}}$ (m)	Diameter DD (m)	Distance dd (m)
1 (base)	60	33.9	67.8	7,280
2	55	31.0	62.0	6,673
3	50	28.2	56.4	6,066
4	45	25.4	50.8	5,459
5	40	22.6	45.2	4,853
6	35	19.8	39.6	4,247
7	30	16.9	33.9	3,640
8	25	14.1	28.2	3,033
9	20	11.3	22.6	2,427
Top Temple	12	6.8	13.6	1,456

$$r = \frac{l}{\sqrt{\pi}}$$

with

l := length of the side of the Kukulkan' Pyramid

With diameter

$$D = \frac{2L}{\sqrt{\pi}}$$

and apparent angle of the sun

$$\alpha \approx 0.00093 \text{ rad}$$

The distance is

$$d = \frac{D}{\alpha} = L \cdot \frac{2}{\alpha\sqrt{\pi}}$$

Hence

$$d \approx 122.33 \cdot L \text{ (scale constant)}$$

Hence the distance by levels using approximate length of sides

This means that the radius of the circle that is associated with the length size of the Kukulkan' Pyramid **R**; must be considered at a distance of observation of "**dd**".

Now consider "Squaring the Circle" reference [1] and lets suppose that the sun (represented by the circle of center **S**) is at the top of the pyramid (hour 12); i.e. the center or the circle **S** and the center of the Square that represents the ceil of the pyramid are the same.

Main approximation established here; considerate that segment **TPS** and the parallel lines that give shape to the square; are collinear to the "Western staircase".

Taking this square to construct another circle using "Squaring the Circle" ; and also taking the line that defines sun position form "sunearthtools.com"; can be established that the position of the circle that is constructed since the circle that at the top of the pyramid; is a the position of the sun at 15-16 hrs

Kukulkan' pyramid with sun position by hours

Model 2

Kukulcan' Pyramid with model 2 "Squaring the Circle" on top and circle at 15-16 hrs

Remember that the phenomenon of the "descending snake" happen between 15:30 hrs and 17 hrs; lasting around 10 minutes on the point where "seven triangles of shadow are projected on the North Staircase" and being able to be observed over a longer period of time.

Kukulcan´ Pyramid with Model

6 Conclusions and Future Work

Analysis of "Model 2" shows that a square can be constructed since an ellipsoid that have like major semi axis and minor semi axis the the dimensions of the ellipse formed by the Earth orbiting the Sun; and a circles that are constructed taking as axis of reference the "Semi major axis" and the "Latus rectum" of such ellipse; while such square was constructed using "Squaring the Circle" [1] .

Another 3 circles were constructed on the remaining sides.

This model was taken to establish that the circle could represent the disk of the sun and the square the base of the pyramid; with a relation with the apparent radius of the base of the pyramid and the disk of the sun; such approximation was used to represent the position of the sun at 12 hrs using a circle of "similar size" at the top of the pyramid to formulate the hypothesis that a second circle with position to the left of the top (circle of hour 15-16) can be constructed using the reference of the "Squaring the Circle [1] to " produce the shadow related with the descending of the snake" at the Kukulcan´ Pyramid.

Following this arguments next speculations have arisen

* Is there a relationship between the KT segment and the equinox line?

Kukulcan ´ Pyramid with Model of Equinox Line

* Which is the relation between the ellipse and the number of steps and levels on the Kukulcan ´ Pyramid

If the position of "Pegasus Constellation" can be found on sky around the equinox day (March 21st); there exist a relation between the "square" shape of the constellation and the base of the pyramid ?

Map of Sky with Pegasus Constellation

* How Mayans use Sun position to define "time zone"?

* Were these assumptions made by the Maya to establish a system of constellations like the Greeks?

7 Note:

Discussion about distortion on images in Google Maps

[Q1 \(on spanish\)](#)

[Q2 \(on english\)](#)

8 References

* [Map at StellariumWeb \(to select location\)](#)

* Microsoft Copilot Bing

[QA1 \(in spanish\)](#)

[QA2 \(in spanish\)](#)

[QA3 \(in spanish\)](#)

[1] Diaz, J. R. A. M. (2024). Vector Projection of a Construction Made with a Rule and Compass to Understand Squaring the Circle.

[2] Martínez Díaz, J. R. A. (2025). Archaeoastronomy of Kukulcan Pyramid using an Squaring the Circle Construction Part I. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17122164>